

STRATEGIES OF VOCABULARY REINFORCEMENT FOR ADULT LEARNERS

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Abstract. *When learning to read, expanding a student's vocabulary is fundamental and involves more than simply mastering a list of words with which students will be familiar. The ability to use vocabulary is much more important: in communication, learning, and knowledge of the world around us. When considering the motives for teaching a foreign language, it is necessary to note the fact that they are interconnected with the student's surrounding social environment, which to a certain extent has a positive or inactive influence on their occurrence and formation. Therefore, we believe that a change in the status of a foreign language in the country and an unfavorable political situation complicate the formation of positive motives with the vocabulary of language learning. The importance of knowing the meaning of words and using vocabulary in the reading process can be compared to mastery of music, which allows you to create a complete piece of music, or with paints, with which, when mixed and applied, a painting is created. Numerous studies in the field of teaching reading indicate that vocabulary acquisition in elementary school plays an important role, as it contributes to both text decoding (recognizing words in a text) and the development of reading comprehension skills. On the one hand, students have difficulty reading words they do not understand. On the other hand, they will not understand the meaning of what they read if they do not know the meaning of most of the words in the text. The practice of teaching reading shows that if students significantly expand their understanding of key words in the text they are reading, then fluency and understanding of the text read as a whole increase.*

Keywords: *readings, dictionary, exercises, assignments, students, teaching, education, formation of new words, grammar, linguistics, information, technology.*

The main problem of learning vocabulary is the retention of all introduced and fixed words in the students' memory, right up to the end of school (we can practically talk about 80% of words, minimum – 60%). This requires repeated (over 20 times) use of each of them for a long time at optimal intervals (from 1–3 days at the beginning of the organized use of a word to 1–3 months at the end of this period). The organization of 90% of such repeated uses of passive vocabulary and 30–50% of active vocabulary lies with the author of the textbook. However, more than half of the repetitions of active and about 10% of repetitions of passive vocabulary should be provided by the teacher during speaking in the lesson. To do this, the teacher must include in the project of each lesson a list of not only new, but also words repeated in it (poorly learned, not used for a long time, in need of reinforcement). There are a variety of ways to enrich students' vocabulary, and here are a few strategies to help you achieve this.

English methodologist Andrew Walkley said: "Without grammar you can say little, without vocabulary you can say nothing." One cannot but agree with this statement. Without denying the importance of studying grammar, we understand that much more meaning is contained in words, rather than in grammatical structures.

Enriching students' vocabulary is the most important task of a foreign language teacher. There are two goals for enriching vocabulary:

- quantitative increase in words and qualitative improvement of the existing vocabulary;
- learning the ability to use known and newly acquired words.

We try to realize both of these goals in our lessons.

To begin with, it is useful to know that in the science of language, it is customary to use a special term to refer to vocabulary - "lexicon". It is perfectly suited to convey the essence of the concept of "vocabulary". It is important to understand that the lexicon is not just an archive of words, but a whole complex of vocabulary units of the language that society uses and people own.

And here we must immediately clarify that having a vocabulary and using it are two different things, and should not be equated with one another. Lexicon includes:

Active vocabulary. This includes the set of words that we use every day, constantly, communicating with family, friends, work colleagues and everyone around us. These are also words that we hear from other people and can be freely inserted into our speech without really thinking about their meaning. We use active vocabulary not only in oral speech, but also when we write letters, SMS, messages on social networks, etc. The main features of an active vocabulary are considered to be freedom of use and the absence of any need to make efforts to select certain words or search for their meanings in memory.

Passive vocabulary. Here are all the words that we know, including those whose meaning we easily understand when they come across us in someone else's speech, the Internet, or written sources. However, these are all words that we use in our speech very rarely or not at all. It is easy to guess that the passive vocabulary can be several times larger than the active one in volume. Naturally, if necessary, we can delve into our memory and find words from the passive vocabulary, but in ordinary life they serve as unused "baggage".

External vocabulary. This definition is most often used in psycholinguistics to refer to words that a person does not know and that relate to specific areas of knowledge. If we come across such words in someone's speech or text, we will not understand their meanings. The external lexicon can be called a "blind spot", within which archaisms, neologisms, professionalisms, highly specialized concepts, terms, etc. are found.

It is not always possible to determine clear boundaries between different types of vocabulary, since they are quite blurred and can constantly shift in one direction or the other. Plus, you need to understand that, for example, a child just starting school can speak literally a couple of thousand words, and by the end of school there are already about five thousand of them in his vocabulary. And, in principle, this amount is already quite enough for everyday life; almost all of these words are actively used.

If a person continues to study, read and learn new things, his vocabulary can expand to ten thousand words, but a huge number of them will already belong to passive vocabulary. But the vocabulary of true scholars and intellectuals sometimes numbers up to 50 thousand words. Of course, only a small part of them will be actively used. The rest will be used by such people to communicate with similar scholars or in the process of reading specific literature. At the same time, their passive vocabulary for most ordinary people will be in the zone of external vocabulary.

The exercises and techniques proposed below for the development of speech and vocabulary are perfect for children and schoolchildren, as well as for students and adults. There are no special rules or instructions for their implementation, except for one thing - they must be

applied, and the more often you exercise, the better results you will achieve. Let's start by looking at three groups of tasks, and then give some useful recommendations.

General exercises for vocabulary development

Exercises from this group can be performed orally or in writing:

Exercise "Alphabet". You need to come up with sentences whose words begin with each letter of the alphabet in order. For example: "Antosha wanders in the thick of the trees, eats honeysuckle, yawns. And the beauty of the forest sweetly, tenderly enchants..." etc. Try to come up with sentences using all the letters: from A to Z.

Exercise "Nouns". You tell a short story using only nouns. For example: "Morning. Coffee. Car. Office. Computer. Dinner. Evening. Street. House. Entrance", etc.

Exercise "Verbs". Similar to the previous exercise, you tell a short story using only verbs. For example: "I came, I saw, I conquered."

Exercise "Adjectives and adverbs". Everything is done, as in previous exercises, only using adjectives and adverbs.

Exercise "Monophone". You come up with sentences in which all words begin with the same letter. Words must be connected to each other. It is desirable that the meaning be preserved, but at the first stage you can give yourself a break and not think too much about the meaning.

At first, performing these exercises will not be easy, especially for schoolchildren and children, but with practice the results will become better: it will become easier to compose interesting sentences and stories, and new words will gradually appear in everyday speech.

Simple and Fast Techniques for Developing Vocabulary

As we already know, the development of speech and vocabulary is necessary primarily for voicing thoughts and conveying meaning. If you constantly train, this skill will develop, but if you do not pay attention to it, it will become weaker. Based on this, to develop a vocabulary, you need to communicate with people as much as possible, pay attention to the new words they use, remember their meaning and apply them in speech yourself.

Here we can give two main tips:

It is useful to communicate with diverse and different people. Among them may be: acquaintances, buddies and friends, classmates, fellow students and colleagues, training partners, salespeople in stores and fellow travelers in taxis and public transport, people on social networks and forums, etc. In other words, the size of your vocabulary largely depends on the breadth of your social circle.

Listening to audiobooks is equally useful. This tool is quite effective and requires almost no effort from you. In addition, it is very convenient: you can listen to audiobooks (as well as seminars and all kinds of training) in headphones on the way to work or school, in the car during any trips, at home, while doing housework or cooking. If you wish, you can find special books for developing vocabulary, collections of quotes and aphorisms, biographies, philosophical and scientific works, works of art and much more.

The techniques presented are suitable for schoolchildren, students, busy people and businessmen, as well as all those who do not have free time for special classes to expand their vocabulary. If you have no problems with leisure time, and you want to spend time usefully, turn to the following remedies.

Special techniques for developing vocabulary. To implement these techniques, you will have to specifically set aside time for them. But the effect will be much stronger than when

performing general exercises and using simple and quick tools. Vocabulary development is facilitated by:

Memorization. If you not only listen and learn new words, but also try to memorize them, you will increase your chances of enriching your vocabulary, and at the same time begin to transfer many words from a passive vocabulary to an active one. As you know, the best way to remember something is repetition, so in your spare time it is useful to retell the speech of other people, excerpts from books you have read, etc. Try to be as close to the original as possible, to preserve the author's style, as well as his manner of presentation. It is also equally effective to memorize poems, songs, and even definitions of various concepts.

Learning foreign languages. You cannot limit your vocabulary to words of only one language. Studying English, Turkish, Spanish and any other language helps expand your vocabulary in several directions at once. Firstly, the more new words you learn and remember, the more connections you make between them and the easier and faster you can "snatch" the right word from your memory. And secondly, by studying foreign words, you become familiar with words in your native language that you did not know before. By the way, an interesting fact: there are approximately 500 thousand words in the Russian language, about 250 thousand in English, and about 50 thousand in Japanese.

Keeping a diary. Suppose that for some reason you cannot start learning a foreign language now, you do not want to listen to audio books and you do not want to communicate with a large number of different people. There is still a way out - keep a diary. Writing for yourself is not a super effective way, but it can help anyway. Pick up a notebook or notebook and start writing something down there every day. Due to the fact that you will constantly be forced to formulate your thoughts, your vocabulary will begin to grow on its own, because you will need to select certain words, including those that are in the area of the passive vocabulary. A bonus will be training your literacy and testing your knowledge of the rules of the Russian language.

Linguistic games. Specialized games such as word puzzles, charades, rebuses, crosswords, scanword puzzles, etc. greatly contribute to the development of the vocabulary of children, schoolchildren and adults. When you solve them, you will automatically learn new words and their meanings. In addition to this, on the Internet you can find many interesting games to expand your vocabulary, which are great to play in a group. Here are just a few: "Hidden Motives", "New Dictionary", "One Day in the Life", "Sound Images" and "Taboo". And here, too, there is a bonus - the general development of thinking and intelligence.

Reading. Websites, books, newspapers and magazines serve not only as a source of information, but also as a tool for replenishing vocabulary. Naturally, when choosing what to read, you need to build on your individual goals and interests. Depending on which "profile" vocabulary you want to expand, you can select specialized, scientific, journalistic or fiction literature. It is recommended to read for at least an hour every day, and to assimilate words faster, it is better to read aloud, because Memorization occurs more effectively when spoken. If you want to focus on individual words, then you can study all kinds of reference books and dictionaries: spelling books, rare words, synonyms, explanatory books by different authors and others.

The exercises and techniques we have proposed should be enough to fill your head with a variety of different words, concepts and terms. It is best to resort not to just one method, but to use several at once. You can even choose a specific activity for each day. And if with exercises, foreign languages and linguistic games everything is quite simple, then with books it's quite possible to

get creative. Therefore, we want to advise you to read not just everything and anything, but something specific.

Books for vocabulary development

Books are always good because they allow a person to learn a lot of new and interesting things. Reading in itself makes speech more developed and rich, but not all books will be useful for these purposes. There are universally recognized writers, authors of real masterpieces that demonstrate the beauty of the great Russian language (and language in general) as much as possible.

Let's start with the Russian classics, which influenced the formation of Russian speech, as well as morality. Books by the following authors will help to significantly expand your vocabulary:

Communicate with people, read books, study dictionaries and encyclopedias, write down new words in a diary, notepad or on stickers - all these are components of the development of speech and vocabulary. If you want to expand your child's vocabulary, read aloud to him, look at and describe wimmel books, play board and active games, make words from cubes and magnets and explain their meaning, support his curiosity and interest in the world around him.

Active and conscious actions are a prerequisite and guarantee of vocabulary development. Human speech can be compared to a muscle that requires constant training to grow and strengthen. Try to always keep it in working order, without skipping or ignoring new words, learning, clarifying and remembering their meanings. And the most important thing, of course, is the use of new words in your everyday speech.

The use of the latest information technologies in classes with a foreign language dictionary allows the use of student-oriented interactive educational technology, helps to overcome the psychological barrier in using a foreign language as a means of communication, increases the effectiveness of learning and the quality of education. For example, when working with computer technologies, the role of the teacher changes, whose main task is to support and guide the development of students' personalities and their creative search. This principle of cooperation and joint creativity is the basis of modernized education. The main goal of teaching foreign languages with a dictionary is to freely navigate a foreign language environment, and this is greatly facilitated by new multimedia innovations, which are defined as "information learning technologies that integrate audiovisual information of any form (text, graphics, animation, etc.), implementing interactive dialogue user with the system and a variety of forms of independent information processing activity." Information technology is understood as a process that uses a set of means and methods for collecting, processing and transmitting data (primary information) to obtain new quality information about the state of an object, process or phenomenon (information product).

In recent years, the term "dictionary" is often synonymous with the term "computer technology", since all information technologies are now in one way or another connected with the use of a computer. However, the term "information technology" is much broader and includes "computer technology" as a component. At the same time, information technologies based on the use of modern computer and network tools form the term "Modern information technologies" (1.66). Information and communication technologies are understood as software, hardware-software and technical tools and devices operating on the basis of microprocessor-based computer technology, as well as modern term means and systems for broadcasting information, information exchange, providing operations for collecting, producing, accumulating, storing, processing ,

information transfer and the ability to access information resources of local and global computer networks.

The use of information and communication technologies in the educational process with dictionary studies causes significant changes in its organization, methods, and forms. In a word, ICT claims to model the learning process as a whole. For example, learning platforms, unlike computer programs, do not work with specific content, but only set the forms in which each educational material can be placed.

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One of the terms widely used with the dictionary is used in practice if information technologies are digital educational resources. In the process of teaching a foreign language, a variety of digital educational resources are widely used (Power Point presentations, On-line tests, training programs, electronic textbooks, Internet educational resources, etc.), which aim students at successful results. Unlike traditional methods, the use of information technologies guarantees the effectiveness of perception and memorization of educational material, saving educational time (3.43). With Words, the leading position among Internet technologies from a didactic point of view is occupied by learning management systems (LMS - Learning Management Systems). They are also called distance learning systems (DLS), learning platforms, and e-learning platforms. These platforms use a wide range of Internet technologies. Learning platforms are educational environments for providing online training courses, maintaining and managing them, and administering the learning process. The student has the opportunity to access the educational environment at any time, in any place where there is Internet access, which ensures the implementation of the principle of individualization of learning: the student goes through the material at his own pace, he has the opportunity to choose the sequence of completing tasks. Internet technologies as the main form of information technology play a positive role in the formation of foreign language communicative competence of students, because Effective learning of a foreign language is based on working with authentic audio, video and printed materials.

The systematic use of information and communication technologies in the process of teaching foreign languages has the following results:

- improving the organization of classes,
- increasing the cognitive activity of students,
- activation of the creative potential of the student and teacher.
- save time (no need to go to the library);
- receive current news;
- use a wider range of periodicals;
- save time for the teacher when preparing a lesson (some texts are already didacticized: they have dictionaries, questions and assignments).

Thus, the use of ICT in the teaching process radically changes the content of the educational system. The organization of the educational process becomes individualized, makes it possible to focus it on each student, increases the positive motivation of students to learn, qualitatively changes self-control and monitoring of learning results, and timely adjusts both teaching and learning activities.

When teaching a foreign language, it is necessary to take into account all these features and the fact that many of those students who will take the matriculation exams want to take exams in a foreign language and choose the language in which they feel more confident. Therefore, their demands on the teacher increase regarding the provision of additional materials on vocabulary, grammar, and thematic support.

Many people want to be sure of their achievements in a foreign language and ask to check them using tests that will be included in the exams. Consequently, at this stage of learning, interest in a foreign language increases and greater demands are placed on the teacher.

During this period, students have a particularly strong desire for knowledge, and more interest is shown in the content of learning than in its process. It was believed that the main reason was insufficiently developed educational and cognitive motives. Therefore, it is necessary to use different teaching methods, including elements of innovative teaching in traditional teaching, as well as developing problem-based learning.

It is known that in the process of learning, new motives can be formed on the basis of old motives. To do this, it is necessary that cognitive and social motives turn into meaning-forming ones, i.e. enriched with personal meaning. And for the student at this time, motives related to his future profession have a personal meaning. Consequently, professional motives will prevail in the student's motivational sphere.

The student pays great attention to setting goals, since for him the main goal is to graduate from school and enter a university, and in order to achieve this, he has to overcome various obstacles associated with learning. Therefore, he is forced to monitor his successes and set, depending on their significance and implementation, more and more new goals, not always being able to choose for himself which of them are important and which are secondary.

When considering the motives for teaching a foreign language, it is necessary to note the fact that they are interconnected with the student's surrounding social environment, which to a certain extent has a positive or inactive influence on their occurrence and formation. Therefore, we believe that a change in the status of a foreign language in the country and an unfavorable political situation complicate the formation of positive motives with the vocabulary of language learning.

In this case, some motives weaken, others strengthen, some motives become imaginary (named for the people around them), others are really active (undisclosed), students are forced to

be hypocritical, hiding their real motives for studying the dictionary language. An analysis of the motives of different categories of students showed that didactic, communicative and aesthetic motives are little used by teachers to stimulate motivation, which indicates that teachers and educators do not sufficiently use techniques (techniques) and methods of teaching associated with the student's personality, know little about his inherent strategies, tactics, teaching styles, as well as poorly oriented in their pedagogical actions towards one or another type of student.

Currently, one of the most important tasks, the solution of which is necessary to increase the motivation of students, is considered to be the study of assimilation and learning strategies associated with the student and the learner. The more strategies a student knows and can apply when learning a foreign language, the more effective his mastery of speech activity will be.

There are as many attempts to classify strategies as there are attempts to define them.

O'Malley and Chamot (1990) based their classification on research and divided strategies into three groups:

- 1) cognitive strategies;
- 2) metacognitive strategies;
- 3) social, affective strategies.

They include cognitive strategies as strategies that have an operational or cognitive-process function (for example,

"repetition" - imitation of a language model, "notes" - recorded information that was presented orally; translation, deduction, etc.).

Chamot considers meta-cognitive Strategies to be those strategies that are associated with planning, monitoring and evaluation. They perform an executive function (for example: "relating new information to those concepts that remain in memory - "information processing").

Chamot refers to affective (social) strategies as strategies that a student uses to establish contact with other students or native speakers ("collaboration", "clarification of an unclear word through a question").

Rubin (1987) distinguishes three groups of basic Strategies used by students.

The first group consists of assimilation strategies. They are directly related to the development of the language system that the student builds. These include cognitive and metacognitive strategies.

Rubin defines cognitive strategies as operations used with dictionaries when solving a problem that requires direct analysis, transformation or synthesis of the material being studied, and names six main cognitive strategies directly related to language learning with a dictionary:

- 1) verification; 2) guessing (inductive inference); 3) deduction;
- 4) practice; 5) memorization; 6) control.

The strategies of the second group - communicative - are used by students to communicate with other people. They serve to overcome difficulties in communication or the lack of knowledge necessary for speaking in communication.

The third group consists of social strategies. They are used to awaken initiative when communicating in a foreign language (talking about films watched, books read).

To date, the most convincing, in our opinion, classification was proposed by Rebekka Oxford (1990) on the basis of a special questionnaire she compiled (SILL "The Strategy Inventory for Language Learning" - "A detailed description of acquisition strategies used in language

learning”). For our research, this classification is very significant, since R. Oxford considers strategies as a focus on the development of communicative competence.

Rebecca Oxford's classification, in our opinion, is the most complete and modern for the reason that it was carried out on the basis of research conducted on students studying the Russian language, and not just on those studying Western languages. In addition, Oxford points out the connection of strategies with the competencies of students, as well as with the dictionary, options for using strategies for four types of speech activity.

The researcher formulated the requirements for strategies and believes that strategies for mastering a foreign language should:

- 1) help in communication;
- 2) help build the student's language system.

In addition, strategies must have the following features: 1) they contribute to the acquisition of communicative competence;

- 2) allow the student to be independent (control his own progress);

All direct strategies require mental activity, but each

the group has its own characteristics. Thus, the group of memory strategies reflects students' abilities such as grouping words, associations, and restoration; they are associated with memorizing words, memory, and are very important when teaching vocabulary. Memory strategies often link verbal communication with visual communication (a combination of photos, drawings with captions underneath). Visual memory contributes to better comprehension in students, whom we call “vyzols” and whose type of thinking can be classified as visually figurative, accepted in psychology, since their memory strategies at the visual level are much higher than at the verbal level. Scientists believe that memory strategies work most effectively if the learner uses them simultaneously with metacognitive strategies that serve to reduce anxiety. Memory strategies are especially important when learning foreign languages, since the ability to remember the right word or expression motivates the student to continue communication and the desire to learn the language.

Thus, when teaching reading to students with different levels of vocabulary, the teacher solves the following tasks: Expand the volume of words that students need to understand in the learning process. Often many words are not used in everyday life, but are significant for learning (for example, in mathematics - the concepts of “dividend”, “divisor”, “quotient”; in Russian - the concepts of “noun”, “verb”, etc.) . Use indirect means of speech influence on students' vocabulary, that is, influence with a variety of reading materials, creating an environment “rich in words” (in speech, reading and writing). This module presents work in this direction with a “word wall” and graphic organizers. Work not only on learning new words, but also on using them in different contexts. Students must know how and when to use the words they are learning and be able to apply them in speech and writing. Enrich the arsenal of methods and techniques that can be used by students to work on determining the meanings of words (referring to various dictionaries, visualization, categorization, graphic organizers). Time to read. Vocabulary Thus, when familiarizing yourself with this module, the teacher will: clarify his understanding of the importance of vocabulary for students; learn what strategies are effective in expanding students' vocabulary; Get acquainted with a variety of exercises to expand students' vocabulary.

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